

PREPARATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF METAL FLAKE PARTICLES/RESIN COMPOSITE

Y. Sako¹, T. Kurose², and H. Ito^{1,2*}

¹ Graduate School of Organic Materials Science, Yamagata University, Yamagata, Japan

² Research Center for GREEN Materials and advanced Processing, Yamagata, Japan

* ihiroshi@yz.yamagata-u.ac.jp

Keywords: Composites, Epoxy Resin, Metal Flake, Mechanical Properties, Reinforcement Efficiency

ABSTRACT

The use of planer reinforcement is considered to have advantage in terms of mechanical properties compared with fiber reinforcement with isotropic dispersion in the in-plane direction because two-dimensional strengthening and stiffening effects can be inherently expected [1-2]. A flake particle reinforced composite, which can be produced by mass productive processes such as compression molding, was fabricated in this study. The objective of this research is to clarify relationship between mechanical properties and internal structure of the composite. The composite was prepared by mixing epoxy resin and aluminum flake including 20 and 30 vol%. The mixture was charged on a metal mold and cured in a hot press machine at the temperature 100 °C for 3hours. Demolded composite was able to be machined to dumbbell test piece shape and mechanical properties and internal structure were analyzed. The observation of a cross section in the composite revealed that many aluminum flakes were well dispersed in the epoxy resin matrix and the aluminum flakes were oriented to the in-plane direction of the composite. The composites material exhibited higher tensile and bending modulus than neat epoxy resin. Tensile and bending strength however decreased as the addition of aluminum particles increased. The observation of fractured surface after mechanical tests revealed that the aluminum flakes were not broken. The interfacial strength between the aluminum flake and the epoxy resin matrix would not be strong enough to break the aluminum flakes by translating the shear force from the epoxy resin matrix to the aluminum flakes. Despite incomplete orientation of aluminum to the in-plane direction and insufficient interfacial strength between the aluminum particle and the epoxy resin, high reinforcement efficiency factor 0.36 in tensile modulus of the composite was confirmed. The potential of the planer reinforcement composite to realize high reinforcement efficiency was confirmed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) is widely used for automotive and aerospace structural applications for their outstanding specific strength, stiffness, and chemical and heat resistance. FRP composites having isotropic fiber dispersion in the in-plane direction are often used when input loads from multiple direction are expected. The reinforcement efficiency of the FRP is limited due to their fiber shape and isotropic dispersion. In case the composite is formed with plastic deformation such as a compression molding, dimension accuracy also can be another issue caused by anisotropic shrinkage due to anisotropic fiber orientation. The use of planer reinforcement is considered to have advantage compared with the FRP because two-dimensional strengthening and stiffening effects can be inherently expected. The improvement of the dimension accuracy is also anticipated because the composite would shrike isotropically. B. Glavinchevski et al. reported that the reinforcing efficiency in strength of a platelet reinforced composite became 0.55 [1] although that of FRP with isotropic fiber dispersion is theoretically limited to 0.375. The composite in the report was reinforced by large platelet (the diameter of the filler is 20mm) and fabricated by hand lay-up process. A flake particle reinforced composite, which can be produced by mass productive processes with plastic deformation such as compression molding, have not been fully investigated and realized. We have fabricated the epoxy resin composite including metal flake particles by the compression molding to confirm the

effect of reinforcement and dimension accuracy of the composites. The objective of this research is to clarify relationship between mechanical properties and internal structure of the composite.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Epoxy resin was prepared through a curing mixture among a main material, a curing agent, and a curing accelerator. Bisphenol A (jER828, Mitsubishi Chemical Corp.) was used as the main material. Average molecular weight is 370 (catalog value). An acid anhydride type curing agent, 4-Methylcyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic Anhydride (EPICLON B-570-H, DIC Corp.), was used. An amine type curing accelerator, 1, 2-Dimethylimidazole (1,2-DMZ, Shikoku Kasei Co., Ltd.), was used. The curing mixture selected in this study can be cured at relatively low temperature and short period of time. The material composition of the curing mixture is shown in table 1. The aluminum particles-filled epoxy composite material was prepared by adding aluminum flake (MG 1000, Toyo Aluminum Co., Ltd.) into the epoxy resin. The average diameter and thickness of the aluminum flake are 30 μ m and 0.3-2 μ m, respectively (catalog value). The aluminum metal flakes are employed because of the ductility of the metal and availability of various aspect ratios flakes. The volume fraction of aluminum particle in the composites were 0, 20, and 30 vol%.

Material composition in epoxy resin (wt%)		
Mail material	Curing agent	Curing accelerator
53	47	1

Table 1: Compounding ratios of aluminum particles-filled epoxy resin composite.

2.2 Preparation and curing of composite materials

The epoxy resin was first stirred by a rotary revolution type mixer and the aluminum flakes were added followed by stirring once again. A degassing step was then carried out using a vacuum degassing machine. The degassed mixture was charged onto a lower mold (10mm x 150mm) and applied to the second degassing step in a vacuum oven. The mixture was processed under reduced pressure and at the temperature of 40 °C for 20 minutes. Thereafter, an upper mold was covered and followed by the hot press molding step. The same experimental procedure was also applied to neat epoxy resin samples. The dimension of demolded composite was 10mm x 150mm x 1.8 mm (thickness) and the demolded composite was machined to dumbbell and rectangular test piece shapes for mechanical testing.

2.3 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Thermal analysis (non-isothermal) of the composites were performed to analyse the curing time at curing temperature of 100 °C with differential scanning calorimetry (Q200, TA Instrument Japan Inc). Samples cured in different curing time at 100 °C were prepared and glass transition temperatures of the samples were analyzed. The measurement were performed with 5.0 ± 1.0 mg in nitrogen atmosphere from 30°C to 180°C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

2.4 Tensile test

Tensile tests were performed by using a universal testing machine having a 5-kN load cell (Autograph AGS-X, Shimazu Corp.). They were carried out according to the JIS K7161 standard, and the crosshead speed was selected to be 2 mm/min. The tests were repeated at least three times for each type of composites to check for repeatability. In order to obtain the results of the test accurately, we performed to remove initial deflection at 1 mm / min until a stress of 1 MPa was transmitted to the sample.

2.5 Bending test

The bending strength and modulus of the composites were determined using a three-point bending test machine according to the JIS K7017 standard. The tests were conducted with the universal testing machine at constant crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. A span length and thickness of samples were 50 mm and 1.8mm, respectively. The tests were repeated at least three times. We performed to remove deflection at 1 mm / min until a stress of 1 MPa was transmitted to the sample in order to accurately obtain the results of the test.

2.6 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

The orientation and dispersion of aluminum particles in the composite material were observed by SEM (TM3030 plus, Hitachi High-Technologies Corp.). A sample was embedded in epoxy resin and polished with a polishing machine (ML-150P, Maruto Instrument, co., Ltd.). The polished cross section of sample was observed and analyzed. Moreover, the fractured surface after the mechanical test was also investigated by SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Figure 1 (a) and (b) show the results of the DSC measurements for the neat epoxy resin and the epoxy composite including 20 vol% aluminum particles, respectively. Glass transition temperature (T_g) of neat epoxy resin increases and leveled off after a curing time of 1 hour, and the curing would complete in 1 hour. On the other hand, the T_g of the composite material increased gradually even after 1 hour and reached similar T_g of neat epoxy resin at the curing time of three hours. We therefore selected curing condition of neat and composite materials at 100 °C for 3 hours.

Figure 1: T_g of samples at the curing temperature of 100 °C and at various curing time. (a) neat epoxy resin and (b) composites containing aluminum 20 vol%.

3.2 Tensile test and bending test

Figure 2 (a) and (b) show the results of the tensile test and the bending test, respectively. The strength and modulus values were summarized in figure 3. The composites material exhibited higher tensile and bending modulus than neat epoxy resin. Tensile modulus of the composite did not improve by increasing aluminum content from 20 to 30 vol%. The improvement of bending modulus for the composites by increasing aluminum contents from 20 to 30 vol% was slightly confirmed. The tensile and bending strength decreased as the addition of the aluminum particles increased.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curve in (a) tensile test and (b) bending test.

Figure 3: Tensile and bending test results (a) Maximum Strength and (b) Elastic Modulus

3.3 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

The results of internal structural observation are shown in Figure 4 (a) and (b). The images show that the aluminum flakes were well dispersed over the composite material. The diameter of the aluminum particles is from 20 to 40 μm . Voids were not visible in the cross-section area. It would be therefore safe to state that our degassing and stirring process under reduced pressure would be appropriate. It was confirmed that the aluminum particles were mainly orientated to the in-plane direction. When we charged the mixture of epoxy and aluminum particles onto the lower mold, the mixture covered about one third of the mold surface area, and therefore the mixture must be compressed and the aluminum particles would orientate to the flow direction.

Figure 5 (a) shows SEM image of aluminum flakes powder and Figure 5 (b) shows fractured surface area of composites. The fracture area was observed from the parallel direction to the thickness direction. Many aluminum flakes, which were not broken during the mechanical test, were observed. It is assumed that the interfacial strength between the epoxy and the aluminum flakes would not be enough to break the aluminum flake. Since the interface is weak, the peeling would occur during mechanical testing and would result in defects which initiate the fracture of composite.

3.4 Reinforcement effect

A reinforcement efficiency factor (REF) of aluminum flakes in the composite was determined by using following equation (1).

$$E_c = \alpha V_f E_f + (1 - V_f) E_m \quad (1)$$

where α is REF, E_f is a filler elastic modulus, E_m is a matrix resin elastic modulus, and V_f is a filler volume content.

In case the tensile modulus ($E_m = 6.57\text{GPa}$) of composite including aluminum 20 vol% ($V_f = 0.2$) is applied to above equation, the REF is 0.36. It is known that the REF of composites with isotropic fiber dispersion in the in-plane direction is theoretically 0.375. M. Hashimoto reported that that of experimental results for CFRP was 0.29 [3]. Despite the aluminum orientation and the interfacial strength between aluminum particle and epoxy resin are not enough as shown in SEM observation, high REF value 0.36 was confirmed. This result supports the potential that the planer reinforcement will bring high REF of composite in modulus and strength.

Figure 4: SEM micrograph of composite material (20 vol%) (a) 200 times and (b)1,500 times.

Figure 5: (a) Aluminum flakes and (b) fractured surface of the composite material (20 vol%).

4 Conclusions

The aluminum flake reinforced epoxy composite including 20 and 30 vol% aluminium filler, which can be produced by mass productive processes with plastic deformation such as compression molding, was fabricated. The observation of a cross section for the composite revealed that many aluminum flakes were well dispersed in epoxy resin matrix and were mainly oriented to the in-plane direction of the composite.

The composites material exhibited higher tensile and bending modulus than neat epoxy resin. The tensile and bending strength decreased as the addition of aluminum flakes increased. The observation of fractured surface after flexural tests showed that the aluminum flakes were not broken, and the interfacial strength between the aluminum flakes and the epoxy resin matrix would not be enough to break the aluminium flakes by translating the shear force from the epoxy matrix resin to the aluminum flakes. Despite the aluminum orientation and the interfacial strength between aluminum flakes and epoxy resin are not enough, high reinforcement efficiency factor 0.36 in tensile modulus of composite

was confirmed. The potential to achieve high reinforcement efficiency by two-dimensional strengthening and stiffening effects was confirmed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported by JSPS KAKENHI for Scientific Research on Innovative Areas “MFS Materials Science (Grant Numbers JP18H05483)”, and also supported by Casio science promotion foundation (8th and 9th research support program).

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Glavinchevski, and M. Piggott, Steel Disc reinforced polycarbonate, *Journal of Materials Science*, **8**, 1973, pp. 1373-1382.
- [2] J. Rexuer and E. Anderson, Composites with Planar Reinforcements (Flakes, Ribbons)-A Review, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, **19**, 1979, pp. 1-11.
- [3] M. Hashimoto, T. Okabe, and M. Nishikawa, Development of thermoplastic press sheet with in-plane randomly oriented and dispersed carbon mono-fiber and evaluation of the mechanical property, *Journal of the Japan Society for Composite Materials*, **37**, 2011, pp. 138-146.